

Granulometric and Sedimentological Analysis of Kerri-Kerri Formation Exposed Around Potiskum, NE Nigeria

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Article History:

Received: 23.11.2025 Revised: 18.12.2025 Accepted: 19.12.2025 Published: 22.12.2025

Abstract

This research investigates the sedimentological properties of sandstones of the Kerri-Kerri Formation exposed around Potiskum and environs. The study aimed to evaluate the textural characteristics, depositional environment, and sedimentary processes that influenced the sedimentation of the formation. Field mapping and sampling were carried out with the selection of 10 representative samples used for the granulometric analysis was carried out using sieve method. Statistical parameters, including mean grain size, sorting, skewness, and kurtosis were determined using the different methods outlined by previous researchers. The results revealed that the sandstones are predominantly coarse to medium grained, poorly sorted, and mostly positively skewed with leptokurtic to mesokurtic distributions. These features indicate deposition under moderate to high fluvial environments. Sedimentary structures such as massive bedding and biogenic burrows further support a fluvial deposition setting influenced by periodic current variations. The study concludes that the Kerri-Kerri Formation sandstones in Potiskum were deposited mainly in a fluvial system with minor deltaic and lacustrine influences. The findings contribute to understanding the sedimentary evolution of part of the Nigerian sector of the Chad Basin and provide baseline data for future geological and resource investigations in the area.

Keywords: *Sedimentological, Kerri-Kerri Formation, Potiskum, Nigeria.*

Suggested citation: Lailai, H.A., Mohammed, Y.B., Gazali, A.K., Hauwa, I.G., Kuku, Y.A., & Sadiq, H.I. (2025). Granulometric and Sedimentological Analysis of Kerri-Kerri Formation Exposed Around Potiskum, NE Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 4(1), 29-40. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2026.4\(1\).04](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2026.4(1).04)

Introduction

Sedimentological studies using granulometric analyses are essential in understanding the textural characteristics, depositional environments, and provenance of sedimentary deposits. This analysis offers insight into the transportation history, energy conditions, and sediment source, contributing to broader geological interpretations such as basin evolution and paleoclimate reconstructions.

Granulometric analysis reveals a range of grain sizes from fine to coarse, with moderate to poor sorting and varying degrees of skewness and kurtosis. Granulometric analysis includes grain sizes, sorting, skewness and kurtosis. The sedimentological studies of the Kerri-Kerri Formation are interpreted to have formed in a complex interplay of fluvial, deltaic, and marginal lacustrine environments.

The Kerri-Kerri Formation is a Paleocene continental sedimentary unit extensively exposed in northeastern Nigeria, particularly around the Potiskum area of Yobe State. It represents the youngest sedimentary sequence within the Upper Benue Trough and southeastern portion of the Chad Basin. Composed predominantly of ferruginized sandstones, siltstones, and minor clay units, the formation has drawn significant geological interest due to its distinctive lithological features and potential for understanding Tertiary sedimentation in the region. Sandstones of the Kerri-Kerri Formation are characterized by a mix of fluvial, deltaic, and marginal lacustrine depositional environments, with evidence of both shallow and continental influences.

Despite various geological studies on the Chad Basin and the Kerri-Kerri Formation, detailed granulometric and sedimentological assessments of surface outcrops within the Potiskum axis remain limited. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the grain size distribution, sorting, roundness, sedimentary structures, and depositional characteristics of the Kerri-Kerri Formation in this area to infer its depositional environment and sedimentary history.

Potiskum is located in the southwestern part of Yobe State, northeastern Nigeria, lying within

latitudes 11°30' to 11°45'N and longitudes 10°55' to 11°15'E (Fig. 1). The study area is easily accessible via the Kano–Maiduguri highway, with several road networks and footpaths leading to outcrop locations. The topography is relatively flat to gently undulating, typical of semi-arid savanna terrain, facilitating ease of geological fieldwork.

Figure 1. Drainage Map Showing the Location of Potiskum (Study Area) and Environs

Figure 2. Geological Map of Nigeria
Source: Obaje *et al.*, (2006)

The Kerri-Kerri Formation was first named by Falconer (1911) who dated it as Eocene and

correlated it with the Cretaceous Sandstones in the Bida and Sokoto Basins. The formation seems to be Unaffected by folding, but dips gently to the North and North-East below the Chad Formation in the Nigeria sector of Chad Basin (Dike, 1993). Figure 2 is a geological map of Nigeria showing the location of Chad Basin in Nigeria and its geological distribution.

It is a continental sequence which was deposited under a wide range of conditions. Lacustrine and deltaic type sediments form the most frequently re-occurring strata. (Carter *et al.*, 1963). The Formation consists dominantly of grits and ferruginous sandstones and clays.

The age of the formation has been a subject of considerable debate. However, Adegoke *et al.* (1986) on the basis of new paleontological data conclusively showed that the formation is of Paleocene age. The formation unconformably overlies the eroded and tilted beds of the Gombe Sandstone.

Stratigraphic Successions of Nigerian Sector of the Chad Basin

The Bima sandstone is the oldest stratigraphic unit in the Chad Basin. It was deposited under continental environment. The formation consists of thin to thick beds of fine to coarse grained feldspathic sandstone of variable colors from white, brown, reddish-brown to grey. The coarse-grained textures are common towards the basement. It lies unconformably on the basement complex. The Bima Sandstone represents the upper part of continental interclaire in Nigeria. The formation is diachronous and probably of Albian-Turonian age (Carter *et al.*, 1963).

The Gongila Formation is a transitional sequence between the underlying continental Bima Sandstone and the overlying marine Fika Shale. The formation consists of thin to moderately thick interbeds of shale, silty sandstone and sandstones. The shale is grey to dark grey while the sandstone is of variable color from brown, white, yellow, and purple to grey. The sandstone texture ranged from fine to

coarse grained. Volcanic intrusives which occur as dolerite sills are present at several horizons of the formation. Shales adjacent to the intrusives have become thermally degraded and are very brittle to soft. The formation was dated as Lower Turonian (Carter *et al.*, 1963).

The Fika Shale is a fully marine unit of the Chad Basin. It is composed of blue-black shale and thin intercalated of limestone. The shale is locally gypsiferous. Volcanic intrusives occurs as dolerite sills are also present at numerous horizons of the formation. The eruption of the volcanics has thermally degraded to the adjacent shales which have turned very brittle and soft. The formation has maximum thickness of 890m. It is diachronous and has been assigned as Turonian-Maastrichtian age (Carter *et al.*, 1963).

The Kerri-Kerri formation consists of thin and thick beds of sandstones, grits and clays in the study area. Coarse gravel is locally common. The clays are usually massive and gritty. The color of the lithofacies varies and ranged from reddish, brown, pink yellow, purple to grey. The sandstone is locally cross bedded and ferruginized. The formation is more extensive and varied in some places where three distinct lithofacies comprising of ferruginous sandstones, kaolinitic sandstones, and laterites have been recognized. The unit was dated Paleocene on the basis of pollen and pores (Carter *et al.*, 1963; Adejoke *et al.*, 1986).

The Chad Formation is the youngest stratigraphic unit in the Nigerian sector of the Chad Basin. It consists of sand and clay. The sand is not cemented with angular and subangular quartz grains. It is fine to coarse grained and of variable color from yellow, brown, white to grey. The clay is massive and locally gritty in texture due to the present of angular and subangular quartz grains. The color is as variable as that of sand. Three separate sand bodies with thin interbeds of clay, clayey sand and sandy clay are present in the formation. Thick sequences of clay separate the sand bodies from each other. The formation is Pleistocene in age (Carter *et al.* 1963).

Table 1. Lithostratigraphic Succession of the Nigerian Sector of the Chad Basin

Age	Formation	Lithology	Thickness from Seismic data (M)*	Average Thickness (M)**	Depositional Environment
Pliocene/Pleistocene	Chad Formation	Clay, Sand	800	400	Continental
Palaeocene	Kerri-Kerri Formation	Coarse sand, Claystones, Shales		150	Continental
Turonian- Santonian	Fika Shale	Blue- Black shale with volcanic	0- 900	430	Marine
Turonian	Gongila Formation	Shale, limestone and sandstone	0- 800	420	Marine/Estuarine
Cenomanian	Bima Sandstone	Sandstone, shale and clay	2000	3050	Continental

Source: Modified from Carter *et al.*, 1963 by Olugbemi *et al.*, 1997

Materials and Methods

Materials

The materials used to carry out this study include;

Several samples were collected during the mapping process, but only Ten (10) samples were subjected to laboratory analysis.

Global positioning system (GPS): -this was used in obtaining longitudes and latitudes as well as the elevations of various locations. It also gives direction during the mapping process.

Mechanical shaker - this was used to separate and analyze particle size in a sample.

Method

The method used in this study includes the followings;

Field Mapping

The method adopted for this research is traversing the study area on a topographic map of a scale of 1:25,000, in which all the rocks exposed and the structures encountered in the field were described and documented. Several samples were collected but only ten were selected for the lab analysis most of which are sandstones.

Laboratory Analysis

Granulometric Analysis

Granulometric analysis was employed to determine the particle size in sediment samples.

Sieve Analysis

Ten (10) sandstone samples were selected for lab work. Samples were disaggregated in the laboratory with a rubber padded pestle as suggested by PettiJohn, (1975). 100g of each disaggregated sample was measured using a weighing balance as test portions for sieve analysis. The test portions were sieved with a Rotag shaker for 5 minute using a set of sieves with mesh size 0.5 phi apart. The sieves were arranged according to decreasing mesh sizes with the smallest opening at the bottom which collects the finest grain and the top is covered with a lid. The sieves and the bottom pan were fastened to the mechanical shaker. Sediments fractions on each of the sieves and the bottom pan were weighed and recorded. Cumulative curves of the grain size distribution were plotted from the sieve result. The univariate and bivariate parameters were computed based on Folks and Ward (195), Miola and Weiser (1977), and Sahu (1964).

During the process of sieve analysis, precaution was taken in the separation of the sieve to avoid the spillover or pouring away of the sediment fractions retained on the sieves after shaking.

Results and Discussions

Field Description of Lithologic Units

The main rock type observed in the area is mostly sandstones. Five (5) separate rock

outcrops were identified and many samples were collected, but only ten (10) samples were selected for the sieve analysis, each carefully labeled (L1A-L5B) as detailed in Table, with coordinates of each location documented.

Table 2. Location of mapped areas with coordinates

S/NO.	Locations	Altitudes	Latitudes	Longitudes
1	LOC 1A	432	11°40' 00.6"	11°05'51.2"
2	LOC 1B	428	11°40'16.3"	11°05'40.7"
3	LOC 2A	422	11°40'23.3"	11°05'16.4"
4	LOC 2B	420	11°40'32.8"	11°05'12.4"
5	LOC 3A	416	11°40'43.6"	11°05'20.2"
6	LOC 3B	414	11°40'38.6"	11°05'16.3"
7	LOC 4A	412	11°41'58.2"	11°04'02.5"
8	LOC 4B	409	11°42'46.3"	11°04'05.5"
9	LOC 5A	400	11°43'32.2"	11°03'09.5"
10	LOC 5B	398	11°43'22.1"	11°03'01.2"

Sandstone

The dominant lithofacies in this region is characterized by cemented sandstone, which has been shaped by biogenic activity and weathering over time. These natural processes have resulted in observable signs of burrowing and erosion on the rock's surface. Sandstone in the Kerri-Kerri

formation is predominantly coarse to medium grained.

Cumulative curves against particle size for 10 samples to ascertain the depositional environment (Table 3). While Table 4 is Summary of traced values of the grain size parameters from the cumulative weight curve for the sample and the corresponding phi (ϕ) values.

Table 3. Sieve Analysis Data for Ten (10) Locations

S/NO	Sieve Size	Loc 1A	Loc 1B	Loc 2A	Loc 2B	Loc 3A	Loc 3B	Loc 4A	Loc 4B	Loc 5A	Loc 5B
1	2mm	28.79	23.91	34.22	31.23	7.21	8.29	12.19	12.8	17.3	8.78
2	1mm	31.52	28.44	16.16	15.93	10.79	14.01	24.57	25.48	28.23	26.98
3	850 μ m	5.67	6.06	2.8	2.84	3.84	3.28	4.79	6.6	5.95	6.69
4	710 μ m	4.17	4.84	2.48	2.34	3.69	3.55	4.8	5.06	5.76	6.13
5	500 μ m	7.4	8.34	5.49	5.88	16.45	17.68	13.52	10.05	8.9	11.09
6	425 μ m	2.6	2.86	2.94	2.98	4.26	4.02	4.86	4.06	4.63	4.49
7	300 μ m	2.96	3.43	2.66	3.42	15.56	14.8	5.75	4.35	4.2	5.33
8	250 μ m	4.18	5.18	8.48	7.84	13.69	16	6.83	7.26	5.45	10.32
9	150 μ m	5.38	7.48	10.9	12.48	18.24	13	14.95	10.31	8.83	11.08
10	63 μ m	5.92	6.16	11.96	12.3	4.89	4.56	6.23	10.83	9.43	7.49
11	Pan	2.51	3.09	1.84	1.99	0.66	0.71	0.75	1.49	0.92	9.65

Table 4. Summary of Traced Values of the Grain Size Parameters from the Cumulative Weight Curve and the Phi (ϕ) for the Samples

Phi ϕ	L1A	L1B	L2A	L2B	L3A	L3B	L4A	L4B	L5A	L5B
ϕ_5	-1.9	-1.9	-2	-2	-1.1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2
ϕ_{16}	-1.6	-1.4	-1.6	-1.6	-0.1	-0.4	-0.9	-0.9	-1.1	-0.7
ϕ_{25}	-0.9	-0.9	-1.2	-1.1	0.4	0.2	-0.5	-0.5	-0.7	-0.3

ϕ_{50}	-0.3	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	1.3	1.2	0.6	0.5	0.1	0.5
ϕ_{75}	0.9	1.2	1.9	2.1	2.0	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.7	1.9
ϕ_{84}	1.7	2.1	2.6	2.6	2.3	2.2	2.5	2.5	2.2	2.2
ϕ_{95}	3.3	3.4	3.8	3.7	3.2	2.8	3.2	3.6	3.4	3.4

Figure 3. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 1A

Figure 6. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 2B

Figure 4. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 1B

Figure 7. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 3A

Figure 5. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 2A

Figure 8. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 3B

Figure 9. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 4A

Figure 12. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 5B

Figure 10. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 4B

Figure 11. Plot of Cumulative Weight (%) against Phi (ϕ) for Sample 5A

The results obtained from this study were compared to the standard values of graphic mean, graphic standard deviation, inclusive graphic skewness, and graphic kurtosis as shown in Tables 5 to 8.

Table 5. Standard Mean Scale

Phi (ϕ) value	Size class
-1.0-0.0	Very coarse-grained sand
0.0-1.0	Coarse grained sand
1.0-2.0	Medium grained sand
2.0-3.0	Fine grained sand
3.0-4.0	Very fine-grained sand
4.0-8.0	Silt
8.0-14.5	Clay

Source: Wentworth (1922)

Table 6. Inclusive Graphic Standard Deviation Scale

Phi standard deviation	Sorting
<0.35	Very well sorted
0.35-0.50	Well sorted
0.50-0.70	Moderately well sorted
0.70-1.00	Moderately sorted
1.00-2.00	Poorly sorted
2.00-4.00	Very poorly sorted
>4.00	Extremely poor sorted

Source: Folk & Ward (2000)

Table. 7. Standard Value and Kurtosis Terms

Calculated kurtosis	Kurtosis
<0.67	Very platykurtic
0.67-0.90	Platykurtic
0.90-1.11	Mesokurtic
1.11-1.50	Leptokurtic
1.50-3.00	Extremely leptokurtic

Source: Folk & Ward (2000)

Table. 8. Graphic Standard Skewness Scale

Calculated skewness	Skewness
>0.30	Very positively skewed
+0.30-+0.10	Positively skewed
+0.10- -0.10	Near symmetrical
-0.10- -0.30	Negatively skewed
<-0.30	Very negatively skewed

Source: Folk & Ward (2000)

Table. 9. Summary of Parameters for the Grain Size Analysis of the Study Area

Location No.	Value of mean	Value of sorting	Value of skewness	Value of kurtosis	Standard value of mean	Standard value of sorting	Standard value of skewness	Standard value of kurtosis
L1A	0	1.6	1.4	1.9	Very coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Very positively skewed	Leptokurtic
L1B	0.2	1.7	0.3	1.0	Very coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Positively skewed	Leptokurtic
L2A	0.3	1.9	0.3	0.8	Very coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Positively skewed	Platykurtic
L2B	0.4	1.9	0.2	0.7	Very coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Positively skewed	Platykurtic
L3A	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1.2	Medium coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Negatively skewed	Leptokurtic
L3B	1	1.4	0.4	1.2	Medium coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Very Positively skewed	Leptokurtic
L4A	0.7	1.6	0.0	0.9	Very coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Near symmetrical	Mesokurtic
L4B	0.7	1.7	0.1	0.9	Very coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Positively skewed	Mesokurtic
L5A	0.4	1	0.2	0.9	Very coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Positively skewed	Mesokurtic
L5B	0.6	1.5	0.1	1	Very coarse grained	Poorly sorted	Positively skewed	Leptokurtic

Interpretation of Sieve Values

Using the graphical data obtained from Figures 3 to 12 using the Folk and Ward's (1957) formulae, this study calculated the graphic mean, standard deviation (sorting), skewness and kurtosis for the sandstones. The values were extracted from the graph and substituted into the respective formulas. Table 9 provides a brief

description of the grain size parameters in the study area.

Sample L1A is very coarse grained, poorly sorted, very positively skewed and leptokurtic.

Sample L1B is very coarse grained, poorly sorted, positively skewed and leptokurtic.

Sample L2A is very coarse grained, poorly sorted, very positively skewed and platykurtic.

Sample L2B is very coarse grained, poorly sorted, very positively skewed and platykurtic.

Sample L3A, the sample is medium coarse grained, poorly sorted, negatively skewed and leptokurtic.

Sample L3B is medium coarse grained, poorly sorted, very positively skewed and leptokurtic.

Sample L4A is very coarse grained, poorly sorted, near symmetrical and mesokurtic.

Sample L4B is very coarse grained, poorly sorted, positively skewed and mesokurtic.

Sample L5A is very coarse grained, poorly sorted, positively skewed and mesokurtic.

Sample L5B is very coarse grained, poorly sorted, positively skewed and mesokurtic.

Mode of Transportation

The bivariate plot of standard deviation versus mean sized based on Miola and Weiser (1968) showed that 100% of the samples plotted falls within the fluvial environment.

Figure 13. Bivariate Plots of Mean against Standard Deviation

Source: Miola and Weiser (1968)

Structural Geology

This involves the existence of internal structures, shapes, arrangements and interrelationship of various rock units. Sedimentary structures are largely controlled by tectonic and regression with their characteristics deposits and facies distribution (Osuji *et al.*, 2018). Structures like massive bed, cross-beddings, burrows and cracks are present on some of the rocks encountered.

The sedimentary structures and textures of the study area comprise of massive beddings and biogenic activities. The structures observed are generally grouped into two: primary and secondary.

Primary structures: are large scale features of sedimentary rock formed by physical processes during sedimentation. The structure observed here is *massive bedding*. Massive bedding is beds without apparent internal structures and they suggest rapid deposition of sediments from high energy gravity flows. The massive beddings are common sandstones and the light brown-grey-dark brown sandstones in all the locations of the study area. The fining upward sequence of the beds was suggested to be typical of fluvial environment (Ojo and Ajakaiye, 1998).

Secondary structures: are post-depositional features produced after sediment deposition due to deformation induced physical processes. They form after primary deposition occur or in some cases, during diagenesis of a sedimentary rock. The major structure observed is *biogenic structures*. The biogenic structures are biologically produced structures that were induced by disruption of sediments by the burrowing activities of organisms during feeding. Burrows are noticeable at the study area.

Economic Geology

Economic geology is the study of the formation and extraction of earth materials that have some economic potential in the society. The economic deposits found in the study area and its environment is only of local important of which are sandstones and laterites.

Laterites: are residual deposits of iron and aluminum hydroxides formed by the weathering

of rocks in humid and tropical conditions. They are composed of both hydrated iron oxides and kaolinitic materials and that makes them a good material for building and construction. The iron-rich sandstones and laterites are processed in the pharmaceutical industry to produce drugs and other chemicals due to their own iron content which can supplement insufficient iron in the body.

Sandstones: is a clastic sedimentary rock composed mainly of sand-sized mineral particles or rock fragment. Sandstone occurs when layers of sand accumulate in places like riverbeds, beaches, or deserts, gradually cementing together under pressure to form solid rock. Sandstone is commonly used in Potiskum for the construction of roads, houses, bridges, dams etc. It is also used as a reservoir due to its porosity and permeability.

Further Discussions

The grain size analysis reveals a sedimentary environment dominated by very coarse-grained, poorly sorted sediments. This suggests a high-energy depositional setting where the energy levels fluctuate significantly, preventing the consistent sorting of grains by size. The mix of skewness and kurtosis values indicates a complex history of sediment transport and deposition, likely involving multiple sources or processes.

Detailed Parameter-by-Parameter Discussion

Mean Grain Size (The "Coarseness")

The mean grain size values (Φ scale) are predominantly between 0.0 and 0.7, which Table 5 classifies as "Very coarse grained." Two samples (L3A and L3B) are slightly finer, classified as "Medium coarse grained."

Interpretation: The consistently coarse nature of the sediment points to a high-energy environment. This is typical of areas like:

Beaches exposed to strong wave action.

Alluvial fans or braided streams are fast-moving water that can transport coarse material.

Glacial out wash plains where melt water carries a wide range of sediment sizes. The slightly finer

samples at L3 might indicate a localized area of slightly lower energy or a different sediment source.

Sorting (The "Spread" of Grain Sizes)

Every single sample is classified as "Poorly sorted." The numerical sorting values are all high (≥ 1.0), confirming a wide mix of grain sizes within each sample.

Interpretation: Poor sorting is one of the most critical indicators here. It signifies that the sedimentary agents (water, wind, ice) were not able to separate grains by size effectively.

This happens when energy is highly variable (e.g., storm waves on a beach, flash floods in a river).

Sediment is dumped rapidly, without time for sorting (e.g., in a debris flow or glacial till).

There is a mixture of sediment from different sources.

Skewness (The "Tail" of the Distribution)

There is a clear variation in skewness: Positively Skewed (most common): Samples like L1B, L2A, L2B, L3B, L4B, L5A, and L5B. This means the distribution has an excess of fine material in the "tail."

Very Positively Skewed: L1A and L3B. A strong excess of fines.

Near Symmetrical/Negatively Skewed: L4A (symmetrical) and L3A (negatively skewed, meaning an excess of coarse material).

Positive Skewness is common in beach environments where finer material is winnowed away by waves and deposited offshore, leaving a coarser lag with a "tail" of finer particles trapped between the larger grains. It can also occur when a coarse deposit is later infiltrated by finer sediment.

Negative Skewness (L3A) is less common and can indicate an environment where coarse material is being introduced into a finer-grained area, such as a channel lag deposit.

The variation suggests that the depositional process was not uniform across the study area, with different locations experiencing slightly different energy regimes or sediment supply.

Kurtosis (The "Peakedness" of the Distribution)

The kurtosis values are mixed:

Leptokurtic (Very Peaked): L1A, L1B, L3A, L3B, and L5B. This indicates a very well-sorted central portion of the distribution but with long "tails" of both very coarse and very fine material.

Platykurtic (Flat): L2A and L2B.

Mesokurtic (Normal): L4A, L4B, L5A.

Leptokurtic distributions are often interpreted as sediments that have been reworked by multiple processes or from multiple sources, each process sorting a specific fraction of the grain population. The flat, platykurtic distributions at L2 suggest a more uniform mix without a dominant grain size population.

Synthesis and Environmental Reconstruction

Combining all these parameters allows for a more robust interpretation:

Primary Depositional Environment: The combination of very coarse grain size and very poor sorting is a classic signature of a high-energy, fluctuating environment. The most likely candidates are:

A Beach Environment (Littoral): Strong waves can carry coarse sediment, and the swash/backwash cycle can create poor sorting. The common positive skewness also supports a beach interpretation.

A Fluvial Environment (Braided River/Alluvial Fan): Flashy, high-energy streams capable of transporting coarse gravels and sands, with rapid deposition leading to poor sorting.

Evidence of Process Complexity: The variation in skewness and kurtosis across nearby samples (e.g., L1A vs. L1B, L3A vs. L3B) indicates that the depositional conditions were not static. For example:

Location L3 shows a dramatic shift from negatively skewed (L3A) to very positively skewed (L3B), suggesting two distinct depositional events or micro-environments very close to each other.

The prevalence of leptokurtic distributions suggests that the sediments have been acted

upon by more than one transporting agent, further supporting a dynamic environment like a shoreline or a complex river system.

In this study, the sandstone were mapped out which could have resulted from impact of high current fluvial sedimentary depositional environment.

This exposure consists predominantly of sandstone and laterites which undergo biogenic activities and weathering overtime resulting to visible signs of burrowing and weathering off of the rock. The color is light brown-grey-dark brown.

The result of the granulometric analysis shows that the rock sample were mainly coarse-medium grained sand, poorly sorted, very positively skewed and leptokurtic. Bivariate plots of mean against standard deviation (Miola and Weiser, 1968) plots the samples to have been deposited in fluvial environment.

Conclusion

The composition, provenance, weathering and tectonic setting of Kerri-Kerri sandstone of Chad basin of Nigeria has been assessed using granulometric analysis. The sandstone bodies are coarse-medium sand, poorly sorted leptokurtic and very positively skewed suggesting deposition in a high energy setting, possibly in a fluvial environment. The data are used to plot a bivariate plot of mean against standard deviation (sorting). The color variations of the sandstone bodies are indication of difference in the cementation minerals. All the graphs indicates fluvial environment as depositional environment.

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